

GEOSPATIAL MODELLING FOR ELECTRIFICATION PLANNING USING OnSSET

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Keywords

ANSER : Agence Nationale de Service Énergétique Rural et Périurbain

ARE:Autorité de Régulation du Secteur de l'Électricité

ESMAP: Energy Sector Management Assistance Program

GEP: Global Electrification Platform

GIS: Geographic Information System

HV: High Voltage

IRENA: International Renewable Energy Agency

MV: Medium Voltage

OnSSET: Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool

PV: Photovoltaic

QGIS: Quantum Geographic Information System

SHS: Solar Home Systems

SNE: Stratégie Nationale d'Électrification

SNEL: Société Nationale d'Electricité

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Executive Summary

This study, conducted within the framework of the Energy Modelling Platform Africa (EMP-A) 2026, aims to support the Democratic Republic of the Congo (currently electrified at 21%) in the strategic planning of its national electrification by 2030, in line with the objectives of the National Energy Compact, which targets an electricity access rate of 62%. The study is based on the use of the OnSSET geospatial model to identify, at the national scale, the most cost-effective, technically appropriate, and climate-compatible electrification solutions.

The analysis combines geospatial, demographic, technical, and economic data to compare different electrification technologies, including grid extension, hybrid solar and hydropower mini-grids, stand-alone solar home systems (SHS), as well as wind power. Two main scenarios were assessed: the lowest levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) scenario and the Force Grid scenario.

The results indicate that the LCOE scenario is the most economically viable option for achieving the 62% electricity access target by 2030. This scenario prioritizes the densification of the existing electricity grid in larger settlements, followed by the deployment of hybrid solar mini-grids and stand-alone solar systems in low-density areas. The required investments are estimated at approximately USD 5.6 billion, mainly allocated to grid densification (USD 2.7 billion), hybrid PV-diesel mini-grids (USD 1.6 billion), and SHS (USD 1.28 billion).

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Scope

The purpose of participating in the training was to gain hands-on experience with geospatial modelling tools that aid in electrification planning at the national level. The training focused on the use of QGIS for spatial data processing and OnSSET for techno-economic modelling of electrification scenarios.

1.2. Objectives and Aims

The objective of this study was to examine most cost-effective pathways towards reaching DRC's target of 62% access rates by 2030, examining how different prioritizations affect technology choice and investment cost.

1.3. Connection to DRC's M300 Initiative

DRC has developed a National Compact for Energy aligned with the Africa Regional Energy Compact and the UN Energy Compact. The compact commits to increasing electricity access to 62 % by 2030, leveraging both grid and off-grid technologies. The training directly supports this objective by equipping us with skills in geospatial modelling that are essential for identifying priority areas, estimating investment needs, and evaluating electrification options. By linking planning with spatial data, Malawi can develop cost-effective strategies to accelerate progress towards its energy access goals.

2. Methodology

2.1 Modelling Approach

The Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) was employed for scenario modeling. OnSSET performs spatial least-cost analysis at the settlement level, identifying the most economically viable electrification technology central grid extension, mini-grids (hybrid PV-diesel or hydro), or standalone systems (SHS) for each settlement.

OnSSET operates via a Python script executed in an Anaconda environment using Jupyter notebooks, enabling flexible scenario testing and visualization.

2.2 Data Sources

The data used in this analysis comes from the following sources:

- Demographic: World bank Group
- Grid infrastructure and Hydro potential:
 - Resource Matters (2024);

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- OpenStreetMap;
 - ANSER.
 - Demand profiles: The DHS Program / ICF
 - Solar PV potential: Global Solar Atlas
 - Wind Potential: Global Wind Atlas
 - Administrative boundaries: GADM
 - Generation structure: Autorité de Régulation du Secteur de l'Électricité (ARE)
 - Electrification targets (62% by 2030): World Bank Group
 - PV, mini-grid, and generation cost assumptions: International Energy Agency (IEA).
 - Healthcare facilities: Resource Matters (2024).

2.3 Data Preparation

Raw geospatial and tabular data sourced from national censuses were cleaned, harmonized, and projected using QGIS in the WGS 84 coordinate system (EPSG:32735) for consistent global compatibility.

An Anaconda environment was set up with essential Python libraries. This enabled efficient data fusion, such as aggregating settlement-level demand profiles and overlaying grid proximity layers.

2.4 Assumptions & National challenges

- Start year:2024
- End year: 2030
- Start year Population: 109276265
- End year Population: 127 400 000
- Electrification access rate start year: 21 %
- Target access rate: 62%
- Grid urban electrification ratio: 0.55
- Grid rural electrification ratio: 0.01
- Urban ratio start year: 0.45
- Urban ratio end year: 0.56
- Household Size: Rural (7), Urban (5).

2.5 Scenarios Modelled

As the access rate target isn't 100 %, the strategy of electrification we choose is to electrify first larger settlement according to the national context.

2.5.1 Least-Cost (LCOE) Scenario

This scenario is designed to identify the most economically efficient pathway to achieve the national electrification target by 2030 starting by electrifying bigger settlement first. It applies a least-cost optimization approach, in which electrification technologies are selected based solely on their levelized cost of electricity (LCOE).

The main key assumptions of this scenario are:

- Start year electrification rate (2024): 21 %
- Access rate Target (2030): 62%
- Urban and Rural tier: 6
- Annual new grid connection: 60 000

2.5.2 Force grid scenario

This scenario prioritizes electricity access expansion through grid-based solutions, with a strong emphasis on grid densification and grid extension as the primary means of achieving the national electrification target by 2030.

This scenario represents an ambitious, grid-led development pathway because we didn't find more desegregated DRC grid data and serves to assess the investment requirements, infrastructure demands, and practical limitations associated with accelerating electrification primarily in big settlement first through the national grid.

The main key assumptions of this scenario are:

- Start year electrification rate (2024): 21 %
- Access rate Target (2030): 62%
- Urban and Rural tier: 6
- Annual new grid connection: no gap

3. Results

3.1. LCOE Scenario

By 2030, the LCOE scenario delivers 9.37 million new connections, electrifying about 79 million people. Grid densification is the dominant option, supplying 45.5 million people, reflecting its strong cost competitiveness in big settlement where national grid exists. Grid extension is not selected, indicating it is not economically justified compared to decentralized alternatives. Off-grid solutions play a major role: standalone solar PV serves 15.8 million people, PV hybrid mini-grids 17.5 million, and mini-hydro 0.2 million.

The figure bellow shows the number of electrify people by technology by 2030.

Figure 1: Electrified and unelectrified people by 2030

The figure below illustrates the geographical distribution of different technologies in certain regions:

Figure 2: Repartition of technologies in settlements

Total installed capacity reaches 1,376 MW, led by grid densification and hybrid mini-grids. The scenario requires USD 5.64 billion, the lowest investment among scenarios, but results in 2,369 tCO₂, mainly from diesel backup in hybrid systems highlighting the trade-off between cost minimization and environmental performance.

The graphics below illustrates the power installed (figure a) and the investment cost (figure b) by technology.

Figure 3: (a) Installed power by technology, (b) investment by technology

3.2. Force Grid Scenario

By 2030, the Force Grid scenario delivers the same number of connections as the previous scenario. Grid based solutions dominate, with grid densification supplying electricity to 45.5 million people and grid extension adding 1.68 million, confirming a strong policy preference for centralized supply even where off-grid options may be cheaper. Off-grid technologies play a complementary role, with standalone solar PV and PV hybrid mini-grids together electrifying roughly 31 million people in larger settlements, far from the electrical grid.

The figure below shows the number of electrify people by technology by 2030.

Figure 4: electrified and unelectrified people by 2030

The figure below illustrates the geographical distribution of different technologies in certain regions:

Figure 5: repartition of technologies in settlements

Total installed capacity reaches 1,347.6 MW, led by grid densification and PV hybrid mini-grids. The scenario requires USD 5.94 billion. However, it results in 2,216 tCO₂ by 2030, mainly from diesel generator in hybrid mini-grids.

The graphics below illustrates the power installed (figure a) and the investment cost (figure b) by technology.

Figure 6: (a) Installed power by technology, (b) investment by technology

3.3. Comparison of the LCOE and Force grid scenarios

The following table summarize the difference between the two scenarios:

Indicator (2030)	Force Grid Scenario	LCOE Scenario
Planning Objective	Policy-driven grid prioritization	Pure least-cost optimization
Electrification Target	62% national access	62% national access
New Connections (households)	9,366,052	9,366,052
Population Electrified	78.99 million	78.99 million
Population Without Access	48.41 million	48.41 million
Grid Densification (people)	45.51 million	45.51 million
Grid Extension (people)	1.68 million	0
Standalone PV (people)	15.52 million	15.79 million
PV Hybrid Mini-grids (people)	16.08 million	17.50 million
Mini-grid Hydro (people)	0.20 million	0.20 million
Total Installed Capacity (MW)	1,347.57	1,376.29
Grid Densification Capacity (MW)	793.68	793.68
Off-grid Capacity (MW)	553.89	582.61
Total Investment (USD billion)	5.94	5.64
Total CO ₂ Emissions (tCO ₂)	2,216.17	2,369.36
Overall System Trade-off	Lower emissions, higher cost	Lower cost, higher emissions

4. Discussion

4.1. Insights and Implications of Results

The comparative analysis between the Force Grid and Least-Cost (LCOE) scenarios provides important insights into electrification planning trade-offs for the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) under a 2030 horizon. While both scenarios achieve the target national electrification access, they differ significantly in terms of technology allocation, investment structure, and environmental outcomes. This confirms that the key policy question is not only how much access can be achieved, but how access is delivered.

A major insight is the consistent dominance of grid densification across both scenarios. In both cases, densification electrifies more than 45 million people, demonstrating that reinforcing existing networks is not only a policy preference but also a least-cost outcome in high-density areas. This reinforces the strategic importance of prioritizing densification before pursuing large-scale grid extension.

However, the scenarios diverge in their treatment of off-grid technologies. Under the LCOE scenario, decentralized solutions particularly PV hybrid mini-grids play a larger role, as they are selected purely based on cost competitiveness. This results in a slightly lower total investment requirement compared to the Force Grid scenario. At the same

time, this cost advantage comes with higher CO₂ emissions, driven by increased reliance on diesel backup generation.

These findings highlight a critical implication: least-cost planning does not necessarily minimize emissions, and policy intervention is required to align affordability objectives with climate goals.

4.2. Technologies and Policy recommendations

The results point toward several priority areas for policy action. First, grid densification should remain the cornerstone of near-term electrification efforts, particularly in urban and peri-urban areas where demand density is high and infrastructure already exists. Investments in network reinforcement, loss reduction, and service reliability can yield substantial access gains at relatively low cost.

Second, standalone solar PV systems emerge as a robust and scalable solution for sparsely populated rural areas. Their strong performance under both scenarios confirms their suitability for Tier 3 service levels where grid expansion is not economically justified. It should be noted that if the constraint to electrify larger settlements first were removed, the model would prioritize this option as the most cost-effective technologies, resulting in a much lower total investment.

Third, while PV hybrid mini-grids are effective in meeting higher demand levels, their emissions profile raises concerns. Policies that promote battery storage, cleaner backup options, or gradual diesel phase-out could significantly improve environmental outcomes without undermining system reliability but the investment will be very high. Aligning such interventions with the national compact plan and climate finance mechanisms, including carbon credits, could help offset higher initial costs.

4.3. Limitations of the Study

This study is subject to several limitations. The national grid data specifically regarding MV lines and the locations of the newest existing minigrids built by the PDL 145 Territoires project and ANSER may be incomplete.

The analysis relies on spatial datasets for population, infrastructure, and demand that may contain uncertainties, particularly in remote or rapidly changing areas. Additionally, OnSSET applies static cost assumptions and does not fully capture future technology cost reductions, fuel price volatility, or macroeconomic shocks.

The model also simplifies grid operation by focusing on expansion costs rather than operational performance, reliability, or financial sustainability of utilities. Furthermore, social, institutional, and security-related factors highly relevant in the DRC context are not explicitly represented, even though they may significantly affect project implementation.

4.4. Future Research and Implementation Challenges

Onsset's results can be improved with a more realistic representation of the grid, taking into account its dynamic behavior and the technical constraints.

Enhancing OnSSET with AI-assisted features, such as improved demand forecasting and settlement clustering, offers a promising methodological advancement for addressing data gaps

5. Conclusion

This study applied the OnSSET framework to evaluate alternative electrification pathways for the Democratic Republic of the Congo under a 2030 planning horizon and a national electricity access target of 62% according to the national compact plan. The comparison between the Force Grid and Least-Cost (LCOE) scenarios shows that similar access outcomes can be achieved through different strategic approaches, each involving distinct trade-offs.

A key lesson is the central role of grid densification, if bigger settlements must be electrified first which consistently emerges as the most cost-effective option in high-density areas. At the same time, decentralized solutions particularly standalone solar PV systems and PV hybrid mini-grids are indispensable for extending access to rural and remote settlements. However, the LCOE scenario demonstrates that least-cost planning alone can lead to higher emissions due to increased reliance on diesel backup generation.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that the DRC adopt a hybrid electrification strategy that prioritizes grid densification, promotes low-emission off-grid technologies, and integrates targeted policy measures to limit diesel use. Leveraging the national compact plan based on Mission 300, blended finance, and climate finance mechanisms will be critical to accelerating implementation and ensuring long-term sustainability.

6. References

- Autorité de Régulation du Secteur de l'Électricité (ARE). (2025). *Annual Electricity Sector Report 2024*. Democratic Republic of the Congo.
- Agence Nationale de l'Électrification et des Services Énergétiques en milieu rural et périurbain (ANSER). (2024). *National Off-Grid Electrification Programme*.
- African Development Bank (AfDB). (2023). *Mission 300: Accelerating Electricity Access in Africa*. African Development Bank Group.
- ESMAP (Energy Sector Management Assistance Program). (2022). *Achieving Universal Access to Electricity by 2030: A Guide for Electrification Planning*. World Bank.
- ESMAP & World Bank. (2019). *OnSSET: Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool – User Manual and Methodology*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- EMP-A Uganda. (2025). *Electricity Market and Planning Analysis (EMP-A): Uganda Country Report Using OnSSET*. Energy Sector Management Assistance Program (ESMAP), World Bank.
- GADM. (2024). *GADM database of Global Administrative Areas, version 4.1*. Retrieved from <https://gadm.org/>
- Government of the Democratic Republic of the Congo. (2019). *Plan Directeur National d'Électrification (PDNE)*. Ministry of Energy, Kinshasa.
- Government of the Democratic Republic of the Congo. (2023). *Stratégie Nationale de Développement des Énergies Renouvelables*. Ministry of Energy, Kinshasa.
- IEA (International Energy Agency). (2022). *Africa Energy Outlook*. Paris: IEA.
- IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency). (2023). *Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2022*. Abu Dhabi: IRENA.
- Resource Matters. (2024). *Congo EPELA: Energy Planning and Electrification Data Platform for the DRC*. Retrieved from: <https://congoepela.resourcematters.org/>
- The DHS Program. (2010). *Spatial Distribution of Population in the Democratic Republic of the Congo*. DHS Spatial Reports No. 218. ICF International.
- United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA). (2022). *World Population Prospects*. United Nations.
- World Bank. (2023). *State Utility Performance and Financial Sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Washington, DC.
- World Bank & ESMAP. (2021). *Mini Grids for Half a Billion People: Market Outlook and Handbook for Decision Makers*. Washington, DC.
- World Bank Group. (2024). *Mission 300: Energy Compact for the Democratic Republic of the Congo*.

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